

FEATURES OF TEACHING ENGLISH AT THE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract. The article discusses traditional and intensive teaching methods based on the functional-communicative linguodidactic model of language, and also develops a scheme for teaching students speech communication on professional topics.

Keywords: scientific text, principle of communication, discussion.

INTRODUCTION

Analyzing the problems that a foreign language teacher faces today in a non-linguistic university, we should consider how the social order of society (to prepare a specialist with a good command of a foreign language in a short period of time) is consistent with the requirements of the curriculum of a non-linguistic university and the minimum number of hours in the current curriculum. It seems to us that the goal set can be achieved - to teach a student to talk about the problems of his specialty and understand the speech of native speakers in this regard during a period limited by the academic framework - by combining traditional and innovative methods, but placing a decisive emphasis on the principle of communicativeness both in teaching and in the construction of the teaching materials and teaching aids used [1]. The study of the features of oral scientific speech should take into account the latest data from psychological and methodological science, on the one hand, and the communicative features of the language of the specialty in accordance with the profile of education, on the other.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Traditionally, teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university was focused on reading, understanding and translating specialized texts, as well as

studying the problems of scientific style syntax. Now it is necessary to think about shifting the emphasis in teaching to developing skills of verbal communication on professional topics and conducting scientific discussions, especially since working on them does not interfere with the development of skills, abilities and knowledge, since it is based on them. Oral speech in the educational form should, apparently, be understood as listening or reading, understanding and reproductive reproduction of what has been heard or read in both oral, i.e. dialogic or monologue, and written forms. Thus, we are talking about the implementation of the speech act of speaking in the process of oral communication between two or more people. Recording what has been heard and using a written text as a source of an oral speech act are easily implemented in the classroom [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our opinion, the scheme of teaching English oral speech in the specialty can be built taking into account the following provisions:

- determination of communicative features for most types of texts in this specialty, which are described in the linguistic literature [3], and the means of expressing these features, that is, communicative models;
- determination of communicative features of oral speech and the means of expressing these features;
- comparison of these means of expression and selection of models for their passive and active training;
- determination of the most complete list of communicative features and models of oral speech in the studied specialty and development of a system of exercises for their active training;
- analysis of various communication-oriented types of texts in this specialty, selection of individual types of texts for educational purposes, determination of their main communicative features, models and development of an effective system of exercises for training the selected structural units;

- creation of a "base of preliminary knowledge" for developing speech skills and abilities, i.e. selection and training of word-formation, lexical and grammatical structures necessary for reading, understanding, listening and speaking;
- development and bringing to the degree of automation of the student's educational algorithms for all types of speech activity;
- oral communication from monologue to dialogue and vice versa, using tasks and games of a problem-search nature.

It should be noted that modern didactic principles of suggestibility, clarity, use of audio and multimedia tools, etc. should be widely used in training. When speaking about the system of exercises preceding oral communication, the teacher must remember their general structure and dosage of difficulties: from one difficulty in one exercise to recognizing similar phenomena, about the cyclical repetition of the studied material in small doses over a long period of time, about bringing the skill to automatism, about complicating the exercises, etc., although one of the main and indispensable conditions should remain their constant communicative orientation to oral speech within the framework of specific speech situations of the educational and scientific sphere of activity. Working in a non-linguistic university, a foreign language teacher must be well aware of the features of scientific and technical texts in the studied specialty and, as needed, acquaint students with them. First of all, this is the presence of special terminology, special general scientific vocabulary, specific service vocabulary, certain complex grammatical constructions. For example, Passive Voice, Conditionals, Gerund, Infinitiv, would rather, had better. The basis for teaching in a non-linguistic environment will be a text in a foreign language. The teacher must select those types and kinds of texts in the studied specialty that will help the student to realize the communicative possibilities of speaking. For example, texts can be distinguished [4]:

- by means of transmission: oral and written;

- by the nature of the presentation: description, message, story, reasoning, consideration and their combinations in special types of texts, such as annotations, reviews, etc.;

- by the degree of specialization and attitude to the addressee: research, such as monographs, scientific articles, educational, that is, articles and texts from textbooks, reference books, dictionaries, etc.

As our experience shows, one should start with the simplest descriptions and characteristics and a monologue form of their processing at the very initial stage. Then you can study texts that are more complex in structure and style, but as early as possible try to develop in the student an algorithm of his activity in the mode of the communicative pair “teacher/audio and multimedia means/ - student”, “student - student”.

It is also necessary to select professionally relevant material for work, taking into account the student's prior knowledge of the language and specialty, his age, the purpose of communication, the type of communication, the level of training, etc. After selecting the word-formation, lexical and grammatical structures necessary for mastering the texts being studied, their training begins. It is necessary to constantly remember about the

"dialogical" form of exercises, including when introducing vocabulary [5]. It is also appropriate to train not only terminological and general scientific vocabulary, but also the service vocabulary of scientific prose and the modal-evaluative vocabulary of oral communication.

An English scientific text, in general, is characterized by linguistic economy, expressed, for example, in the nominative nature of a sentence, the peculiarities of terminological systems, special linguistic clichés; a kind of clarity (graphic means of dividing the text and paragraph); thoroughness of presentation (diagrams, tables, repetitions, replacement of some structural units by others). Oral speech has other features - this is the "looseness" of the sentence structure, the predominance of a simple sentence, situational /incompleteness/ of phrase segments, special emotional

coloring, etc., which is described in the works of many linguists [2]. Already at the stage of primary training of speech act structures, there is a need to compare the communicative features of a scientific text and oral speech in a given specialty. Some communicative features and models used to express them are left at the recognition level, while others are actively trained. The grammatical basis of an oral act of communication should, as experience shows, be a simple sentence and the most common types of complex sentences, which should not contain a large number of secondary members. A number of the structures studied may be cliches and phraseological units.

CONCLUSION

Thus, modern methods of teaching foreign languages in a non-linguistic university consist of a combination of traditional and intensive teaching methods based on the functional-communicative linguodidactic model of language and the development of a comprehensive system of teaching students speech communication on professional topics.

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